

Participant 12

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client, product, person, manager, company, team, people, day, issue, developers, quality, provide, work, approach, end user, completely, code, escalation, suppose, fresher

SPEAKERS

Researcher

Participant 12

Researcher 00:20

Hi, Participant 12. Can you hear me?

Participant 12 00:23

Yeah. Please let me know if you're able to see me.

Researcher 00:27

Okay, fantastic. Good afternoon. How you doing?

Participant 12 00:34

Yeah, I'm doing well yourself.

Researcher 00:37

Yes. Doing well, thanks. So we'll get on with the interview and it's Saturday night, India time so I can let you go. Alright. Thanks for the time and the opportunity to do the interview. I really appreciate in this Sunday night, a Saturday night. Okay, let's start with an introduction. Can you please introduce yourself briefly mainly, just tell us your education, your experience in software engineering? Yeah.

Participant 12 01:10

Yeah, so I am like I'm 29. So I almost have around eleven years of experience as a software engineer comm technical data. And now I have done my Master's in Computer Science. Prior to that, I did my bachelor's in computer applications. So I have around five plus years of degree in computer science. Or plus I had an intensive from company like [deleted to preserve the researcher/participant anonymity] under Australian client [deleted to preserve the researcher/participant anonymity] So I got a lot of experience working with clients across the world. The major companies I have worked with are like in USP Pharmacopeia talk about its equilibrium and view to the companies that provide second party products and are currently working with medical line of product. I can't, of course, tell the name of the client product since I'm working right now with it. But currently, what I'm looking at is the insurance

[deleted to preserve the researcher/participant anonymity] that happens right now. Mostly, I've been working as a C sharp dotnet for most of my career, so not as tech is what I am good at.

Researcher 02:15

Okay, fantastic. Yeah. Thank you that that's, that's enough, I think. So your current team, the teams that you answer the question on the email, based on this theme, you're using Agile right Scrum? What are you using Scrum? Okay, fantastic. Can you briefly just describe how the use Scrum?

Participant 12 02:28

Scrum.

Researcher 02:35

Okay, fantastic. Can you briefly just describe how the use Scrum?

Participant 12 02:38

Yeah, so we are using JIRA as a tool for that, where we are handling all your meetings and everything. Usually access in case we have a scrum master in our team, that that that handles all the meetings and whatever the upcoming sessions that we need to look into. So since we are working from remote location, and our client is from a different country itself, so we have to sync up calls that happens. So when that happens in the middle of our when we are about to start our day, when that happens, a sync upon where we made sure internally if we can remove any backlog we are having for the work that we'll be doing today. And then we have our evening scrum call, that's usually the client clients morning when it started. So we just get input from them. So that if there is any backlog that client could resolve. So maybe the next day while we can start working on the product. So it's a 15 minutes session that usually have which has three questions. That's the pattern we follow that what we did in the day, what we are supposed to do, and what's the backlog that we are facing as of now. So that's how it works. It's a 10 day sprint session that happens usually, including Saturday, Sunday. If you take it for dessert, well desperate, in which in the starting, we have the product owner builders who usually get the details, what are the stories that will be coming in this sprint, and we have a refinement session on Monday and Tuesday, two days, since it's been a really big product. So we have two days of refinement metrics up to one to two hours, where we'll discuss the stories and get a pointer values like how much time it might take. And then we have demos on the last day.

Researcher 04:14

They applied to the last day of the sprint right.

Participant 12 04:19

Yeah, get the last night usually it's the second Friday of every month. So in which stakeholders and everyone is there.

Researcher 04:26

Okay, fantastic. Yeah, that's a good implementation of Scrum. This is one of the few where I heard people are doing a good, the good. Following the guidelines to some extent. It's good to hear right. Thank you. Just few question regarding the team and we can move with some of the questions I sent in

the email. So how long have you been working together in this team? What is the size of the team? And the level of self-governance?

Participant 12 04:55

We are 12 developers and the QA team is separate. We have been working with this team for almost nine months now. Okay. I have been working in the same domain for almost three years now, actually usually are similar only working on. There is a lot of control on how we do things and what we say to the client.

Researcher 05:06

Okay. Okay, thank you. You told me the type of software you develop is within the insurance domain. But is it a custom software? Is it a new development? What technology do you use?

Participant 12 05:21

Yeah, so I can provide you an input. So the product has been there since 1992. So they have they started working on it. So usually, it was just a paper and question paper that they used to do in the insurance sector, and over the time, it has become a product. So [deleted to preserve the researcher/participant anonymity] during the COVID, time itself, they have taken around eight companies. So they have gotten those eight company product inside that one product. So it's like a big shot inside the whole insurance sector. So usually just take over the companies in that. So that way, what happens is that whenever they do for a new company, we need to make sure that whatever code set that the old company is providing to us, we have to like make sure that it comes with the product that we are actually providing to the client and it's not an ambiguous port anywhere. So, plus over times, like earlier, we used to have a web forms then we moved to MVP products. And now we are in micro services phase. So that product improvement is also something that we have to do.

Researcher 06:19

So you modernise the product or you maintain in it, you extended the functionalities or you maintain existing functionality

Participant 12 06:30

Yes, mostly enhancements. So in every after fourth sprint, we have an innovation phase. So to speak sort of innovation. The six Sprint's are of where we check all the bug fixes are there if there is an existing or some kind of code cycle that we need to do. After every six sprints, we have two sprints where we provide our input as an innovation thing. We provide the client provider some input, and this is what customers demanded, is it feasible that we can achieve this part? So that when new increments,

Researcher 07:02

So I'm just curious 1992. I don't remember where I was, but it would be considered as a legacy system. I'm just curious why the client didn't replace it and choose to maintain it.

Participant 12 07:16

So the main reason I can tell you is that this client that we are talking about, as of now, it came into the picture in 2005. So in 2005, that company got acquired, and this client bought it, and the legacy system that they are having client don't want to touch it, it is actually afraid that if something because we said we gave a suggestion to the client that why not replace everything and create some SRS solution. And we can move on with some new design. So the clients answer was that most of the end user of this source are either government people, or people who are already in their 50s and 60s. So they don't want even a button event to be replaced in the screen. So that's the main reason that the end user doesn't want.

Researcher 08:00

I've seen I've seen those scenarios. I mean, yeah, yeah. That's not the purpose of the interview, we could have that conversation in another day. I just want to know a little bit about the team. So you said how many people are working currently in the team? Oh, yeah. 16 to 18. Okay, are they cross functional? Or only developers or what type of coding

Participant 12 08:23

The senior manager to the scrum master to the developers and testing team and design.

Researcher 08:31

So it's a cross functional team. Fantastic. Yeah. So, we will be talking about quality software quality and we will discuss in some examples of software quality, but you know, the definition of software quality can be challenging. So, I'd like to share with you the example we use and get you to comment on it. So, we use ISO standards definition, I will read it for you and we can discuss it briefly and move on. So it says software quality is the degree to which the system satisfies the stated and implied needs of its various stakeholders and thus provide value. It's also recommend some quality characteristic which they are not functional in nature, in nature. So they are mainly performance compatibility, usability, reliability, security, maintainability and possibilities. So we could have a whole day to discuss just one of themselves. Briefly, would you agree or disagree with this definition? And would you like to comment on it?

Participant 12 09:44

Yeah. So, technically, this definition is completely correct word while working what I have experienced because it matters we have this definition we give many examples, it is definitions, but when we come into actual product and inside the whole corporate sector, what we use releases, the main concern there is that maintainability is achieved, security is prolonged. And whatever the end users demand are to be satisfied irrespective of whether that ties up with the definition or not in the end user requests of functionality that has to be done in three specific locations. And if you are saying that this code is ambiguous, why don't we change it? And if he says, no, we don't want to change it, just black box leave it as it is. So that's the place where we are not able to achieve some of the quality we want, like quality wise, but the major things is the maintainability and security, these two pillars are minimal requirements.

Researcher 10:36

Thank you. Yeah, I agree with you. Sometimes the it's at the end of the day is the customer who decide what's quality should look like I agree with you. And in many times the client bring their own constraints. And the definition shifts from one focus to another. Yeah, I agree with you. So what do you do to assure quality in the team for this product? What processes what practices do you have? You mentioned, you have QAs, so what other processes you have in place?

Participant 12 11:09

Yeah, so since being Legacy product, first of all, we made sure that we have a whole unit test structure. So testing was something that we wanted. So 100% code testing should have been there before a new product is actually added in it. So there are three phases of testing that we are using, there is an unique tool for unit testing that Microsoft provides us, then there is an US team, they will do the integration testing. And then there is one product level of post production server where they check the whole smoke testing and everything whether the product is feasible or not. So these three testing phase that we usually see, then in from a code perspective, we are using it and some added some time, we use DFS to make sure that check in and everything are properly built. And we are using this new technology of CI CD pipeline using AWS. So using AWS TerraForm, we are actually created as the CI CD pipeline for them. This includes TeamCity, and October's. So we make sure that whenever a new product, unit testing, and everything is done, automated build happens, and it is sent to the QA for testing. And the whole code set is equally managed by the whole team, including we have internal code reviews, and a client side code review prior to the code before the code is sent to the QA for testing. So that way we have minimal issues with a colon the port part is what the client requires. Because clients also provides us kind of architect kind of personal just checks. And we'll just do the code review and make sure that the code is clean.

Researcher 12:38

Okay, great. What other software engineering practices do you use? For example, do you use Continuous Integration do you use? Yeah, what other?

Participant 12 12:55

Yep. Integration. For continuous deployment, we are using octopus TeamCity. It is something that we're using Tara forms. So we have a DevOps team too. Even though there's a client side DevOps team smarter for most of the service, they are the person who actually look into them, we don't get too much involved with those people. But if suppose we are doing any configuration related change, or any isolated change, so those are the people who actually have to talk. So in the CI CD pipeline whenever there comes a bill related issues, so those are the people who talk. Plus, if you talk about the quality assurance and setup, so if you talk about database, so we do make sure of fine tuning and everything that occurs that is working properly. From a practice perspective, and plus a simple call is somewhere we usually on a morning basis with everyone in the team knows where every person is. So it's if someone is only or something so we have another person, another developer handy to make sure the product data is not spill over to the next.

Researcher 13:53

Okay, fantastic. Thanks. We will move to the core aspect of the interview, which is based on the answer I've sent you in the email and we will go through your answers and I will have more questions and we can discuss some examples. So from the answer you provided, my assessment is your work is not really clear to that is a safe work environment. So I will define what we mean by safe so it's not security, but it's a sentiment of safety, which we mean that the work environment provides a sense of security from a precaution so you and your teammates feel it's okay to admit mistakes. You feel that it's okay to propose initiatives and discuss problems within the team. And there is a sense of confidence that the team will not embarrass, reject or punish someone for speaking up or showing mistakes or bringing concern forward. So can you comment on what you think of the safety level in your team?

Participant 12 15:06

So from ideally my own example, rather than giving some other developers so it's something that comes over time with and plus the year of experience also does matter. So as a fresher when I joined the company, even though the team environment might have been okay to work in, but I was myself, like afraid that some issues might come, my manager might spoil. Or maybe the client might just throw me away, and I will be jobless. Those concerns come when you are a fresher and till starting three years of experience I had over times after working around eight to nine clients, there is automatic and confidence level that is better than okay, what I'm providing is something that is up to date. But there comes a time, like I'll give you an example, in the last company I was working on Saturday, Sunday, so I was like half sleepy at around 3am in the morning. So instead of connecting to the dev environment, I actually connected to this SQL environment of production. And the whole data set actually went over there. So by the time the morning, I was awake around, I had around 160 Plus emails from the people I don't even know and designations that I have never seen in my life. Those were those kinds of emails came from all around. And my manager was like supported me it was a supporting like when you do that, I was like I was not sure it was understand that. But there was a prosecution, there were some isolation, and everything happened fast. So I have seen the negative side of what is the business that happens sometimes, even though it was a human error. And that moment of time, I came to know that sometime what happens is the team that's supposed to look after you, they don't even give you a chance to tell you that, okay, this is not an issue. So what happened was I added some extra rows in the database. So I told my manager, there is no data that has been deleted, it's just some addition that could be removed anyways. And even the client didn't have any issue. The person who was in charge from clients and told me okay, it's totally okay, data was already correctly known that. So there was nothing to worry about. But the face of my manager that changed over those two, two days of time showed that okay, no one wants to take that responsibility and that certain period of time, so the team effort actually just vanishes even you are the only person who is like, left upfront, to take all the action that comes.

Researcher 17:16

So yeah, go ahead.

Participant 12 17:21

So, sometimes these things happen when the escalation mark is about a manager's paygrade, I would say. So then when those kinds of things happen, but usually what actually happens is like we are given

a chance in the stand up in the morning that is there some issue that you have done, or there has been a made from the senior club from the client said that there is some issue, so what I'm doing, what's the solution that I could provide them. So those kind of approach as a team effort is given. And during the demo session, when client actually asked okay, why this product has added filler worldwide, this new era is helping in the sprint. So manager usually tells the team was working on this also, as a team effort. See, make sure that not a single developer or a QA person gets all this whole data that could come.

Researcher 18:05

So do you agree, it is not a safe working environment? Would you categorise it as a safe not safe working environment?

Participant 12 18:16

I wont call it safe environment if it's okay with you?

Researcher 18:19

Yeah, a safe work environment. Like I said, it's it means that the work environment provides a sense of security from repercussions. So you feel that it's okay to admit mistake, you feel that it's okay to propose initiative, it feels that it's okay to discuss problems. So you have the confidence that your team will support you, if you propose idea of if you speak up about something or if make mistakes. So that's what we mean by saved.

Participant 12 18:54

So to be completely true, because of the peoples who are working in Indian based companies, these are mostly service based companies. So the safe environment is for the client. So we don't have a safe environment. If the client doesn't like our work if client has something to say to us, so those things into 10 is what the manager tells us. So the environment is safe until unless everything is going the way the client wants. And I am like being completely truthful to you. I don't want to lie.

Researcher 19:23

No, no, no, that's what we want. I mean, this is our research environment, you safe you, your participants. Go ahead.

Participant 12 19:33

Yes, we are in the third world companies, most of the companies are service based companies. So a client is kind of a master for us. Whatever they tell us is something that we need to do irrespective of what timeframe we are working on or how much time we are giving them for to if they want something to be done in two days, we will have to do in two days. There is no extra saved for nights. It's something that we get.

Researcher 19:56

Yeah, I understand the clients Yeah, as long as the client is happy, you are safe. Right? That's what you saying? Yeah.

Participant 12 20:06

So it's not a requirement. There is no safety.

Researcher 20:10

Yeah. So in a scale of five from strongly disagree, disagree, neutral agree, strongly agree. How do you assess the safety level of your team?

Participant 12 20:25

My current team, I would say neutral. Neutral. has not occurred yet. Yet for my last team won't disagree.

Researcher 20:34

Okay, that's, that's a good, good. That's, that's a good candidate for us to talk to. Fantastic. So now we will go through your answer you provided in the email, we'll discuss them. And hopefully you can share with us some examples from your current team or your previous team, because they tend to be similar the previous team, you disagree to a safe, and this team, you seem to be neutral, somewhere in the middle, as long as the client, the US client is happy, it is safe. So the first statement says if you make mistakes on your team, it is often held against you. And your answer says depends on the impact of the mistake. Usually, it's just taking as a team and during internal syncs up called the person responsible, is asked for the reasons. So usually, it's a no Can you elaborate a little bit on this?

Participant 12 21:33

Yeah. So just now, as I explained you, so, it depends on the kind of mistake that you have done. So if suppose your impact, the work that you have done is impacting the end user of the client, then there is no one that will be supporting you, you are just all alone. But if suppose the work is impacting just the code, the code client itself in which that the development team of client itself come across this issue, and it is not the senior management, or the end user stakeholders that are involved. So at that time, it could be internally taken care of, and it is taken as a whole team based issue. So it totally depends on the impact level, like how much farther issue has gone.

Researcher 22:13

So it is it is? How can I say it, it is hostage to the satisfaction of the client in writing? Yeah, as long as we don't compromise the satisfaction of the client, it's okay. That if we compromise the satisfaction and the relation with the client, so would you say you are blind, you are in trouble?

Participant 12 22:36

Yes, you are. anywhere above product owner isn't it isn't a big issue for you. Things that a product owner?

Researcher 22:46

Okay, so can you share me with an example where a mistake was done? Where it has happened?

Yeah, well, we humans, it has happened, and it affected the client or it was escalated to the client. So

the environment is not safe because it was escalated. Can you share with me an example? And tell me what happened? Exactly?

Participant 12 23:12

Yes. So I can give you two examples. One is the one that were in the database, I actually misplace the production data itself. There wasn't any queries to hold data from AWS cloud. So some data was completely brought into production. So overnight, being a Sunday night, so I got multiple emails around 161 170 emails from I will product on at layer from client side, and from my manager side also. So I got multiple emails from senior managers earlier the morning itself, I got calls, personal calls from my manager, and he was asking, like, what would you do? I was just on, I was on a vacation, how could you do this to me and my team, and you have like, completely ruined my day. Even though I'm pretty sure was my day that was supposed to be ruined. So the backstory is that the person the manager, my manager was on leave for three days, he was on vacation somewhere with his family. It was in on December 27, actually, so the client was also the most of the clients are on Sunday. And so was my team. So then there's this kind of escalation, actually, they were not sure what's the impact and how much damage that has been done. So and this reason being and being it's holiday season and everything, so everything was escalated till eighth of January. So from 26 Till eighth of January, there was no response from client or my senior management, that escalation has been taken care of and you are good to go. They were everywhere question marks the length of Jan and oh nine, the client returned and my manager and everyone returned and they were like, okay, it was not that big of an issue. But it's so this was a line my manager quoted to me okay, it was not that much of a big issue. And I was like, what are you kidding me on perform 26 to eighth of January forever. I wasn't able to eat food in the morning because of this was escalation and there was no response as you are supposed to take care of me as a team member and client is, of course supposed to work best since we were not able to deliver what they were asking, and we needed some issue. But being a manager, your only responsibility is to make sure to be a little bit of a shield for us and protect us if in case we are doing some error, that's the whole point of view being here. And then saved did a different escalation on myself to my senior manager that he, he was completely like, he didn't do much work, he was working too much. We told them not to work that much, even though they asked me to complete the task within two days. So it was like, there was a lot of pressure put on me, since everyone was holiday, and I was in pain. And then when the issue came, everyone just vanished. Or when they were told, okay, he was the only one. And we had no hand in this. So it was really big escalation and a lot of learning for me.

Researcher 25:48

So yeah, so what did you learn from this? What did you learn and how it affected you?

Participant 12 25:57

It definitely affected me in a way that post that it's been almost one and a half year now, I have made sure I don't work more than eight hours in it. What I have learned is that we are just workers for the game and being at the lowest level as a developer. It's not that much of a value for me, since there are 1000 more who can take my position. And so you have to play the fair game and you can't just be like, what earlier I was, you would give me something I would suggest my three four solutions, okay, when why don't we do this, I was more enthusiastic towards the task. I had this in my mind, okay, the team is

with me. Now, I lost my enthusiasm, I just do my job. But post that whole eight to nine day of drama, I was like, Okay, it's just a job. It's, I have to do my eight hours complete to my task, go home, and just forget about this. So that completely changed me as a person. And therefore I came to know, okay, why over the years, people usually take the job as well. And they don't want to get that much involved in, like a family or something. And this was one of the reasons that actually changed my mind or mind into this working into the same.

Researcher 27:06

Interesting. Do you think that this type of incident also affected the quality of your work?

Participant 12 27:17

Definitely, I usually used to work for 12 to 18 hours a day. So there's user stories that came for sprint, I used to always take two three stories from the next sprint and use to complete them for the client. So I was giving them extra work. And in return, I was asking for nothing, all I wanted was okay, because I like working. Sometimes you have that joy to work for extra time. Now since after that incident, I was working till 3am, my manager never told the client, okay, the person was working on a Sunday on what countries aren't on period till 3am, Sunday stamping happened, it's okay. Till then until they completed their whole vacation, they didn't even care about okay, the person is suffering over this. So that whole perspective change that, okay, you are just worker and you just need to do your duty and just go home. Even though you do the extra effort, there is nothing that you will get in return. But if something happens in those extra hours, everything can just put on you. So, definitely the mindset change.

Researcher 28:14

Yeah, so the mindset, so, what I hear is your efficiency and you willing to work more has dropped. So does it mean the quality of your code also dropped?

Participant 12 28:29

Yes and no. While quality work is sometimes that actually improved to be truthful or from our productivity because after that incident happened, I started studying more because I wanted to leave that I was not happy with the company itself. So with that, you learn a lot of things while giving the extra time I have and by preparing for certain things you come across and you learn new technologies new stuffs but I do it for myself. I had whatever I do when I have time, I do learn some new products that I learned the dotnet core and all those products so I could implement those things too. So the learning definitely from a growth perspective yes I'm investing more time on myself. But the motivation for code quality has completely vanished. And I have to do in these many tasks every day, I won't do those tasks in one day less than two days, I'll just do what I manage to achieve. But, when they give us enough time to develop our tasks then the quality of my code is better.

Researcher 29:17

So, the effort on you invest in in the quality of your work it was not impacted at all.

Participant 12 29:25

The effort is definitely impacted. The end result is not affected unless we are not given enough. So I'll give you an example. So suppose there is a story that came that would take around three days, but I

am pretty sure I can do it in one day. So if suppose I'm able to do in one day for the next two days, I'll remain white and I'll deliver it on the third day itself.

Researcher 29:50

And you become disengaged and doing the minimum right.

Participant 12 29:55

Yeah, directing the anger towards me they have asked for because anyways also. During that assignment, we do give an input that okay, this can be done in two days. But sometime what happens when you find a certain code and you are able to do it at half day, for those next four to five hours of work that you could do, you won't tell you as a state. Okay? Anyways, if some story comes up three days, and it will take six days, I will be working for eight hours. So why not work the best when I have certain amount of hours left? Then what?

Researcher 30:27

Yeah, thank you. That's a good example. Let's move to the next item, which is about bringing up tough issues and problems. So it stays a member of your team can bring up problem and tough issues. So your answer is yes, it's actually advised by the product owner and leads to counter and say no to something that is not possible. If suppose there is some issue faced by one of the developers the same code every evening is set up and there is no blockage in the development and completion of the task. Can you elaborate a little bit on this? So what type of problems are you talking about here?

Participant 12 31:14

Yeah, so sometime and when the product is sometimes the most, if not the freshers, even as a developer, when we are working for actually for us in the client itself, there are certain problems and issues that come like some of the core part is obsolete. So when you are working on some product, so client is asking this, this button event needs to be changed. And when you go to that port site, you see that the whole code is absolute. And Microsoft is saying, with the next framework, you want to provide it. So that something is someone that I only know, like I am the person who is supposed to convey to the end user, okay, the code is absolute. So you need to provide as a user story or some extra point for code cleaner, because this won't work from the next update, or from the next who's drafted after a year, it will just stop working. So those kinds of updates and code related improvements are something that the client, architect and client owner expects from you. And secondly, when the old discussions are going on using that during the refinement sessions, and also, they just provide us the description of what stakeholder wants. Now how do we need to approach this? What's the business model that we can approach what's the SDLC lifecycle we can move on with both like what whether we go with the waterfall, whether we create a small prototype to the end user and then go with the whole product itself, those different approaches is something that's completely upon us to say, but the minimum requirement is that you have at least two to three years of experience in the product itself. And you have done all that at sessions. Like for freshers this comes in future advice is straight away as to first study or the KT session knowledge transfer sessions, and then given in both of themselves, because they might not know what digestive product could be. So that's what usually happens.

Researcher 33:03

So do you have an example where somebody brought a problem or an issue and how it was dealt with?

Participant 12 33:12

Yes, so during the transfer time, so we had a lot of new developers that joined the company. So over there, we had a developer who recently completed his masters from the US. So he just came back to India with a with a new knowledge of a technology stack. So at that time, MVP was something that was completely new to us, where forms is was playing was using. So he told that we can create rest API's over here, instead of using this approach. So he created that whole model. So the technical lead we had at that time, he told him to create a whole design diagram, at least not the whole document, at least create a design model, kind of a semi architect level, where we can actually demo to the end user, this is the approach we have, could we give it some more time and maybe create a prototype for you. So, everything was going on, but one Monday when the guy came and we had a call with a manager, which will be to happen Monday. Since the title it was the only person who used to have Aiders. So the managers a straightaway told us just a phrase, how can you give some advice towards stop this and it was like a week of effort that was thrown away. And the managers logic was that normally that he knows this so why do we waste our time studying a new product rather than we will just complete our task and move on? And when the time will come then we will learn itself?

Researcher 34:40

That's unfortunate to have such a mentality actually. What's the most is that the teams experience by losing that opportunity to adopt a new solution and technology in your opinion?

Participant 12 34:58

Amazing to know that I would suggest that the company, the like this kind of approach does to newcomers either become completely disengaged, or his attitude becomes whatever why should I care. Either they become this, like the seats in front of the computer and od his work, as the team lead says, or there is a constant, like switch off that goes on, like the person has no loyalty to the company. So, a lot of like, you don't have a resource that is there for at least two to three years, every six to four months, the newcomers just leave the company. Because they know that either we need to keep up with the latest technology if you want a good package, or go to a good company, or we will be just become irrelevant for the rest of our life. So that that mentality comes as a new and that's what happened with me also, like as a newcomer, my master's degree was in Java, but I didn't had a job. So I joined a company that forced me to work on dotnet technology. And even till today I am working on top tech. Even though I don't like it, I would love to put this away.

Researcher 36:01

It's outdated technology now, isn't it? Yeah, yeah, I think it's become, it's become almost a legacy.

Participant 12 36:13

That's what I said.

Researcher 36:14

Yeah.

Participant 12 36:17

In my current company, and the last company that I worked on, still there are products that are going on even though they become irrelevant.

Researcher 36:24

Of course, yeah, they would last for another 10 years, almost. Um, yeah.

Participant 12 36:28

The issue is that most of the degrees that the newcomers are getting by Python dotnet is not even there right now. And most of the most of the companies so to for them to study VB dot entity itself and downgrade because just in these five or six service based companies were having this VB dotnet product, because their end users are way too old. Most of the latest companies are more common words Python, or Java or at least Python is somewhat everywhere we can see nowadays. So this approach is actually killing the resource. In a way the future perspective of the end user is definitely.

Researcher 37:06

Yeah. Do you think that this mentality of rejecting initiatives, the adopter, the adoption of new technology affects the quality of the product somehow?

Participant 12 37:20

Yes, it definitely affects the quality of the product. Because when deprioritize technical growth you create legacy and technical debt. When you say that we don't need to do this, even though you are pretty much sure that this would only resolve the issue, that then product will definitely get affected. And that's the reason most of the time, what happens is the product become a liability because the senior management doesn't want to give you the opportunity to innovate.

Researcher 37:52

So it has a price, it has an economical price, and it has a quality price as well. Yeah. Thanks for sharing that example. I'll move to the next one, which is people on your team sometimes reject other from being different. Mostly no. But your answer says mostly No. But if the person is fresher and has not seen the product and the business behind it, we try to provide some different approaches than that is just bluntly rejected. And they are asked first to complete a knowledge transfer session. Can you explain a little bit what's happening here?

Participant 12 38:36

Yeah. So what happens is whenever these new freshers joined from the we're just part from the policies, and they are as an intern towards working under, so they don't have that much of a knowledge of how the business works. They are good in the technology. So and being a newcomer, they always want to give that input because they have that gene, okay, we want to create something where my name becomes famous. So they always want to give some certain inputs. But what happens is that being this like, like the current product I'm talking about, it's there for since 1992 1993. So there is

certain boundary that if we can't close well, people, there is a certain box that they have created, okay, nothing should go out of this. Because if something goes out of this, we won't be able to handle the whole product. So they have that condition, sir. So like in the last product, we had a resource who came from IIT and just joined as a fresher to us so it is one of the biggest Institute in India, from what we know of it.

Researcher 39:35

Yeah, it's highly regarded.

Participant 12 39:41

So that that guy has a lot of knowledge. He had a lot of ideas. So he was pitching too much. So what happened was that client got so much frustrated because every second to third like he would provide some new kind of approach because he was like, Okay, I have to learn how the business works and then I'll start my own After a certain period of time, so his approach was to get as much business value not just from the client as he wanted. And for that he had to pitch in some input so that he would become like, like a friendly person to the client. So client, he can just directly talk to the client about things. But in the reality in the business world, this doesn't work, like client are not that stupid that they would give their whole business ideas to you, and you can start a competitive company in front of them. That's not how the business world works. And he did that mistake. So every second week, he would teach him something new to that client and client was like, since the client about four months frustrated with a C sent an official mail, and please stop harassing us. We don't want these kinds of solutions, we will provide you what needs to be done. And please have an internal poll and whatever idea you have pitch it to your technical leads. So what he was doing was that he would send personal message to them without concerning the whole team that this is the approach I want to put so that the client would tell okay, this is the guy who's working hard and you guys are not giving that much input, so that he becomes a good. So that's the college mentality, that guy's head, okay, I value some answer to my teacher, indirectly, the teacher would give me an aid. So then the mentality he had. And that's not how the business line works. So there is a hierarchy. Even though nowadays, all companies say that we are removed the hierarchy system, you can directly talk to the manager or the client. But there is a line of hierarchy that stable, so you can't directly just go to the client and pitching your ideas, you will have to follow some process. And so that's what happened over here that I saw from my iPad, okay. People can be stupid when they join. So that that was a solution that actually gave me

Researcher 41:49

Thanks for that example. So let's move to the next one, I jumped the one about taking initiative, because we already discussed that in previous examples. So that's that was enough. I'll talk about the next one about helping each other right. So it says it is difficult to ask other member of your team to help. You said over the years that things have changed a lot. When I started my it journey, there was a fixed hierarchy. And there was an issue. The culture of offices has changed, and team collaborate more. And it's done regularly. What what do you think has changed and IT industry, at least in India display made people more collaborative now?

Participant 12 42:42

Yes. So when I started back in 2012, the newcomers or the developers usually didn't had any speech to talk to the client. So client calls were always taken by the tech lead and the manager. So when you are not there in the meeting, you can never give any idea so whatever idea we had you to the deck Likud. Now according to his understanding, he would pitch it to the end user. So that one to one conversation never happened. And that was the biggest issue I these issues were coming. Secondly, like in the scrum calls, now they have introduced a new product for Israel, that safe approach in which multiple, multiple teams can interact with each other on the same level than just a single team working together. So this self certification is going on right now we have to do by next month, I have to complete that safe certification. So the safe approach in which an inter product team itself worked together to achieve a certain goal. So that actually helps like the DevOps team and my team earlier is meant to collect 1516, we won't even know what the teams that are working with our knowledge of the whole business was never provided. But now what are those that they have changed is, when he joined the company in the first three months itself, they give us an overall idea of the whole product itself. And these are the different products we have, these are the different teams that are working with you. And these are the people to connect in case if you require some help. And this whole thing was completely missing back in the days. And that would cause a computer visit kind of a formation for us that we couldn't cross and that could cause many issues. So that's the number one change that has come across to all

Researcher 44:31

This quality of having access to the client. Now you have access to the client and you have some level of visibility how does it change the dynamic of the work? What, what quality it's brought to the team?

Participant 12 44:52

So first of all, the biggest quality because I will have a developer I'll give you my input so biggest qualities. He got that offered us, okay the person the client is a human like us, it was like a god figure for us we were completely afraid of. So that thing itself is a huge improvement when I can talk to you and tell you, Okay, this is the solution. And what you're telling me is not a good solution. When I'm able to cross question your approach, that's when the improvement in the product happens. When, there is no prosecution, if you hadn't given me an opportunity, I need to work to make sure that approach is fulfilled. Whatever approach I had, I can't give it. So the biggest improvement that over the years has happened. And the biggest reason why the quality of the product has improved over the years from for most of the companies is this approach where the client itself initiates to talk to the developer and ask them whether their approach is correct or not. Because earlier, what happened was, they would ask these things to the technically to the manager. Now the management techniques have stopped development for almost five to 10 years, they have no idea of what the product is going on, right. So they didn't have that approach or solution for them. But now, as a developer, I'm working in the current technology right now. So if you had some question I can directly give you okay, this solution won't work. This is a new solution that you can work on, and completely changes the entries.

Researcher 46:15

So what I understand from your, your statement is this drop in barrier between the developers and the client may give you access to the client, and you get more feedback. And the feedback allows you to

understand better the needs of the client. And you also have the ability to influence the client and to advise the client from a technology perspective, right?

Participant 12 46:48

Yeah, so earlier, we were just a software developer. Now actually, we are software engineer, where we provide an agent, some ideas as an engineer, and we are not just typing developers, so just type the code interview there is there to the clients that that has changed things a lot.

Researcher 47:04

And you mentioned that the quality has also changed.

Participant 12 47:08

Yes, most definitely, the quality has changed, I'll tell you the reasons. So, when you are yourself able to provide a solution and that content is created by you, then there is always a self improvement thing in your mind that you are afraid that the result that you're providing, if it is not correct to maybe the next Tech Network essentially. So that inbuilt desire of giving a better product actually results into that beautiful and big quality product itself. Like if suppose I have given a solution to the client, there is my responsibility to make sure that the solution that I am able to provide at the end is the best quality product and if bank goes somewhere else and asks somewhere else, it should not be a less value product. So innovative product is your kind of the whole solution your content that you're providing the client is said solution always is better.

Researcher 48:05

So why do you provide a better solution because you feel invested in the product?

Participant 12 48:12

It's because earlier also used to provide some better solution but your deadline was the person intermediate report provide the solution to the end user. And sometimes they might not understand some might they might forget in the meeting what we need to tell because a single decade will provide input of around five to six developers. So it could be a human error but right now I am directly contacting my furniture architect of the end client side. So I can directly teach him the solution of a specific question that he has. And from a client perspective what has he has improved is for a different different product he has different different developers so he can directly connect to each of the syllables independently rather than earlier having a tech lead the only person who was presenting everything

Researcher 48:58

So yeah, sorry.

Participant 12 49:01

Yeah, so that middle layer when it is removed, that's the main reason why the whole improvement process has improved a lot.

Researcher 49:09

Yeah, so the middleman has been removed so you have access to the client and you could directly communicate and work with them right. Okay, I'll move to the next item. Wishes no one on my team would deliberately act in a way that undermine my effort. You said yes, no one does it in front of you. But in one meeting with manager there are always one or two person who worked less and try to better the senior Yeah, there have been situation where The work is done by a junior and the lead of a senior show the demo, but I guess they take credit for it, right? Yeah. So did this happen to you? Yeah. How did you feel when it happened to you?

Participant 12 50:19

That's what happened. So, like the template and manager has so much years of experience that we didn't even knew that we have been done this way. It's after a certain years of experience to come to know, okay, this thing was wrong, we were actually betrayed. At that moment of time, the politics has been played so greatly that you won't even know, the newcomer doesn't even know because from the day when he is told that you are not supposed to give the demo users need to do the work and we are the persons will give them but over the years to come to know that plant itself, want the person who has done the development, do the demo. And they will just say to the client that maybe his communication skills are not good or something, they will take some excuse to undermine the person and say, Okay, we will give the demo. And that usually affects the person because if a person when you are in industry, over the years, your overall experience is what needs to get improved if you want to go to a managerial position, or maybe an architect position. So it's not just the development, your communication skills, your documentation styles, your mailing capabilities, your connection with the client, everything matters as a whole, when you want to become a manager or product owner. And that's what something is taken away, because manager always held that fear that the person should not be coming too much fast towards me. And that that whole thing actually changes the whole perspective. Because I have seen people like you can see my communication skills are not that I have been my masters and everything I work with so many peoples over the years. So when I joined the company, for the first time, there were certain meetings that I was not being a part of. And I was told that because I'm from a certain location in India, I had that accent, that client might not understand what I'm saying. So it's okay that I skipped the meeting. And I just sit there and the person instead of me gave the whole interview, our meeting and everything. So that actually in the end, makes you like worried whether your confidence level definitely just vanishes, like okay, you fear your client, like whether the end user is able to understand you or not whether you have made fun of your accent. But it's something that never happens after a certain year

Researcher 52:30

We can I don't think it has nothing to do with your accent you speak good English and it's very clear. So I don't think it has

Participant 12 52:41

If I will say when if the person is having some accent issue client doesn't worry, everyone has their accent. The Australian people have a different accent. The Polish people have different accent the US people these are the three clients I work with.

Researcher 52:55

And Australian and Americans are very used to accents. They are migration countries they are very used to accents. I don't think that anyway that's a mentality thing which happen in these unsafe work environment which you could consider it as unsafe work environment. So what I want to understand as a developer when you've been put into that situation, I mean, your effort was undermined, you will not be able to show your achievement did it affect you in somehow?

Participant 12 53:32

Yes, it definitely affected me there were certain instances so the first manager that I worked at see was one of our very bitter person I would say so when he joined a company I'll just give you an example. So when I joined that company just after around six or seven was my grandfather expired, so I didn't knew that there is a certain leaves that you can take. So six in the morning my grandfather experiment father called me at eight in the morning I came to the office and asked my manager if I can go home I was that stupid because there was a new the company. You don't need to ask permission insisting you can just adequately so my manager at 8am asked me to call my father and tell him that if I can come after two days, the person who has lost his father just a few hours ago, I need to call him and ask him if I can come home two days later. So that was the mentality of that specific moment and whatever name so that's the mentality of the person was he was quite a bit it was. And there's the reason the whole environment was too much and says no one thing they're doing actually like for the NRC, still the main is over their season, our Senior Manager in that company,

Researcher 54:37

Yeah, in places like that. Accountability is not important. I've seen all workplaces like that when they are not safe, and a lot of things are happening. People are not held accountable, and they can stay at work even though with that attitude, so I understand. Yeah.

Participant 12 54:59

So, instead Okay, the first opportunity I got to get rid of the company, even though the pay was good in both the companies I left.

Researcher 55:08

Yeah, I would understand Yeah, nobody would accept those conditions.

Participant 12 55:14

So for me to the manager even called me personally and told me that CBG me and also it was truly iced tea stager, I was so much frustrated with the whole event something that happened.

Researcher 55:27

So, what I wanted to now do you think that that climate in the in the previous team has affected the quality of the work in any shape or form?

Participant 12 55:39

Yes, it has definitely, it has affected the work so much that a release that was supposed to happen in the year, suppose year one happen after eight years. So a product that was supposed to be completed,

if suppose we talk about in 2000. That came out in 2008. So last year, last year, one of my friends told me that okay, that product has been completed. Now. This was supposed to be completed when I was there.

Researcher 56:13

So how was the quality after eight years, I mean, the

Participant 12 56:17

There was no quality itself, it was just an aggressive competing, because the person was so bitter and so bad. That there was constant people who were just being in the company and then leaving being in the company and leaving. So there were like nine to 12 developers who has worked on that specific thing. So the quality is definitely completely rubbish. There is nothing there. The only thing that you can get expect is just a security protocol of OWASP is definitely there. Because that would something that we won't get an issue with. And secondly, the maintenance part, maybe they are looking at it right now also. But the product is definitely a huge, huge a bundle of just I would say primer as of now. There's nothing because if there is something that has came out after eight years, which is supposed to come before it, yes, it is definitely not. in complete contrast with what was there in the market.

Researcher 57:12

Yes, it's outdated already. Right. Yeah, yeah. So I had another question. But I forgot. So yeah. Because people leave in and not stay, and they leave with their knowledge, and you bring a new person and you lose the continuity, right. And that new person may be will struggle and the quality of his work is low, and it creates other issues. Right. Right.

Participant 12 57:44

Definitely. And the thing is that, even though the same related tasks, but as each person will have their own approach, irrespective of if the task is same, and everything. So if there are 12 people with Islam perspective added in a single task, that task will never survive over a certain period of time. Continually motion is completely dead.

Researcher 58:06

Yeah, yeah, I understand. We come to an end. And I'd like to thank you a lot for the good examples and discussion. I enjoyed it very much. But before we leave, I'd like to ask you a final question. We've been discussing about feeling safe and feeling confident at work and contributing and doing quality work. Is, is there anything you'd like to add on this topic that we haven't covered yet?

Participant 12 58:43

Yeah, so. So when I was doing my Masters, there are certain PhD peoples who were studying with me, we're working on this as a methodology. So there are certain features that I would say that people usually who do research in this part usually miss is that the time the methodology that you are looking at from a customer and user like in the US and UK, in Europe, and the methodology that is implemented in the third world countries, which are mostly the people who are actually working on the products, like the couple of people in Southeast Asia, in Vietnam, and all those people who are actively working. So here, there is no safe environment.

Researcher 59:29

No, Your participation is anonymous, please feel free to add if you want to. As I said, in my emails, your participation is completely anonymous. None of your details or the company you mentioned will be made available, so don't worry about that.

Participant 12 59:51

Yeah. So if that's the case, then I can tell you the whole truth that people actually don't tell you. So what's happening is it is a colonial environment. That's it That has not moved on. And I'll give you a short example. What happens is that the US clients or the UK clients, they work from 9am to 5pm. And, and people are working in Southeast Asia, we have to work according to their timezone. So we work from evening to morning 6am. So that our match with them, and we don't get paid for those extracts. Or, or in some cases, when we are getting paid, we are paid \$5 for the whole night.

Researcher 1:00:35

That's not even the minimum wages in Europe or the UK.

Participant 12 1:00:40

That's the reason they are actually providing those products to the southeastern South Asian countries because these deliveries were. So the safe environment that usually does talk about is basically what's the client when till the moment the client or the end user or the cavities comment in the way how long this would say, unless they are happy is what specific moment for us. If my end user says, okay, this person has worked a lot and everything, but we don't want him in our team. So for me, the safety moment ends.

Researcher 1:01:13

Yeah, so I think we discussed this at the beginning, it's hostage, the safety is hostage at the satisfaction of the client, right?

Participant 12 1:01:24

Yeah. And because of that, whatever peoples who are in the head are in charge of us, like the person was manager to me or the senior manager doing the whole workflow of that task is to just make sure that the client is happy. So if suppose there is any kind of issue that has come, they want to for a second to throw us in front of the purse, to make sure that they are safe, and the client remains happy and try and don't just leave them. So any validation or support that you are expecting, will come at that specific moment of time. So that's the environment that's going on right now. Hopefully, over the time, those things might change. But as of now, this is the truth of how the whole life cycle is going on.

Researcher 1:02:07

So how do you think it affects the quality of the product you're producing?

Participant 12 1:02:16

There is a constant fear, because of which there are certain approaches, there are certain things that sometimes think of okay, might this approach might work, but you have a 50/50 like condition that

maybe it has an issue. So those kind of approaches you are never able to deliver to the client. So whenever you add because of which, like there are certain instances in my life, where I have thought of a product, okay, this would have helped me a lot like I was thinking of creating a chatbot for the US based company, I was about to suggest and about it, but I was worried that maybe check mould development might be an issue for some of the people in the team. And so I didn't give them approach. And now two years after, when I'm working on here, they actually client actually have asked them to create a chatbot application. So we would have done started there two years back. But I had a fear in my mind that maybe the team is not capable and nothing makes the client much richer. And because of that fear of rejection from the manager of the client, you actually don't give him that good quality product that you can tell. So you have to have 100% efficiency and development it as a single resource, like you can't have the whole team plan for you. If you have an approach to give it is you who has to complete it. So the quality is somewhat degraded, because as a team, you are not working on it as a single user we're working on

Researcher 1:03:48

Okay, Participant 12 I let you go and it is Saturday night. Thank you very much. I appreciate the honesty and everything's you shared with me today. And I'd like to wish you a good night and we will stay in touch all right.

Participant 12 1:04:05

Yeah, sure. Thank you so much, good night.